

```
public class Course {
    private String code;
    private String title;
    private int credits;

    public Course(String code, String title, int credits) {
        this.code = code;
        this.title = title;
        this.credits = credits;
    }

    public String formatDetails() {
        return String.format("[%s] %s (%d credits)", code, title, credits);
    }

    public boolean isUpperLevel() {
        if (code == null || code.length() < 4) return false;
        try {
            int level = Integer.parseInt(code.substring(code.length() - 3));
            return level >= 300;
        } catch (NumberFormatException e) {
            return false;
        }
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Course c1 = new Course("CS214", "Software Dev", 4);
        Course c2 = new Course("CS21", "Bad Code", 4);
        Course c3 = new Course("CS300", "Advanced", 3);

        System.out.println("1: " + c1.isUpperLevel());
        System.out.println("2: " + c2.isUpperLevel());
        System.out.println("3: " + c3.isUpperLevel());
    }
}
```